

Heterocyclic Steroids : Part I. Synthesis of Naphtho-Pyrimido Thiadiazine and Naphtho-Thiazolo-Triazine

S. K. VASUDEVA†, M. P. MAHAJAN and N. K. RALHAN*

Department of Chemistry, Punjabi University, Patiala-147002

Manuscript received 1 October 1973; accepted 13 March 1974

The synthesis of new heterocyclic steroidal model systems viz. 2*H*,12*H*-Naphtho [1, 2-*c*] Pyrimido [1, 2-*e*] [1, 2, 5] Thiadiazine (V) and 11*H*-Naphtho [2, 1-*c*] Thiazolo [2, 3-*c*] -*as*-Triazine (VIII) is being reported.

THE experience in the synthesis of Benzo-pyrimido-thiadiazines¹ and Benzo-thiazolo-triazines² prompted us to extend the work and herewith we report the synthesis of two new heterocyclic steroidal analogues viz. Naphtho-pyrimidothiadiazine (V) and Naphtho-thiazolo-triazine (VIII). (Scheme-1).

In IR spectrum the absence of bands in the regions 1690-1730 cm^{-1} and 3200-3400 cm^{-1} indicated the absence of $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $-\text{NH}_2$ functions.

1, 4-dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-(1'-nitro-2'-naphthyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (III) was smoothly reduced with SnCl_2/HCl to 1, 4-dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1

Scheme-I

The condensation of 1-nitro-2-naphthylamine (I) with 2-methyl-2-isothiocyano-4-pentanone (II) by the method of Mathes *et al*^{3,4} afforded 1,4-dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-1-(1'-nitro-2'-naphthyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (III). It was noticed that the impoverished amine (I) need the aid of a protonic catalyst (H_2SO_4 or HCl) to facilitate the reaction between I and II.

-(1'-amino-2'-naphthyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (IV). Some of the difficulties inherent in the reduction of the nitro group have already been discussed.^{1,2} TLC of the product IV (eluted with DMSO and developed with iodine) indicated it to be a single product. IR spectrum of IV indicated a strong absorption band at 3200 cm^{-1} due to amino function. The oxidative cyclisation of the reduced product IV with $\text{NBS}/\text{CCl}_4/\text{Pyridine}$ ^{5,6} afforded 12*H*-naphtho [1, 2-*c*] pyrimido [1, 2-*e*][1, 2, 5] thiadiazine (V). IR spectrum of V

† Present address :—T.B.R.L. Sector-30, Chandigarh.

* To whom all correspondence be addressed.

showed the disappearance of original band due to amino function and appearance of a very weak band due to -NH function.

Since we already had an experience, it was thought needless to try the reaction between 1-nitro-2-naphthylamine and phenacyl thiocyanate⁷ for the synthesis of 2-imino-(1'-nitro-2'-naphthyl)-4-phenyl-4-thiazoline (VI), as the product was invariably contaminated with 2-hydroxy-4-phenyl thiazole arising from the intramolecular cyclisation of phenacyl-thiocyanate. Alternatively 1, 4-dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(1'-nitro-2'-naphthyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol and phenacyl bromide via Michael Retrogression yielded VI. IR spectrum of VI indicated a weak absorption band at 3250 cm^{-1} due to $>C = NH$.

2-Imino-3-(1'-nitro-2'-naphthyl)-4-phenyl-4-thiazoline (VI) was smoothly reduced with SnCl_2/HCl to 3-(1'-amino-2'-naphthyl)-2-imino-4-phenyl-4-thiazoline (VII). In its IR spectrum there were three bands at 3400, 3360 and 3225 cm^{-1} due to $-\text{NH}_2$ and $>C = NH$ functions. 3-(1'-amino-2'-naphthyl)-2-imino-4-phenyl- Δ 4-thiazoline (VII) on oxidative cyclisation with NBS/CCl_4 in presence of pyridine afforded 3-phenyl-11H-naphtho [2, 1-e] thiazolo [2, 3-c]-as-triazine (VIII). In its IR spectrum the disappearance of original strong bands due to amino function and in its place appearance of a weak band due to -NH function accounted for the cyclised product.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in soft glass capillaries with concentrated sulphuric acid bath, and are uncorrected. Microanalytical service is from CSIRO, Australia. IR spectra were run in KBr beads and Nujol mulls.

1, 4-Dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(1'-nitro-2'-naphthyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (III) :

2-Methyl-2-isothiocyano-4-pentanone (1.57g.; 0.01 mole) was added in one instalment to a stirred solution of 1-nitro-2-amino-naphthalene (1.88g.; 0.01 mole) in ethanol (25 ml) and a drop of sulphuric acid. The mixture was heated under reflux till the separation of a yellow solid. Solvent was removed under vacuum and solid obtained was treated with 10% sodium carbonate solution (50 ml) and then washed with distilled water (50 ml). The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid. Yield 1.90g; m.p. 232° (d). (Found : C, 62.01; H, 5.49; N, 12.55%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 62.39; H, 5.20; N, 12.84%). NMR(DMSO): δ 1.20-1.37 (s, 6H; $>C(\text{CH}_3)_2$), δ 1.52 (s, 3H; $\wedge\text{CH}_3$), δ 5.01 (s, 1H; $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), δ 7.50-8.30 (m, 6H; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5-\text{C} = \text{CH}$).

1-(1'-Amino-2'-naphthyl)-1, 4-dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-2-pyrimidine thiol (IV) :

1, 4-dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(1'-nitro-2'-naphthyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (3.60g; 0.011 mole) was added to a magnetically stirred suspension of finely powdered stannous chloride (7.45g.; 0.033 mole) in concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 ml) at such a rate so that the temperature of the slurry was maintained

below 10°. After the complete addition of the nitro compound, the mixture was left on a magnetic stirrer for 24 hrs. White slurry thus obtained was diluted with cold water and sodium hydroxide (40%) was added till the salts of tin were redissolved. The solution was chilled for one hour, the white product was collected and air dried. Product obtained was crystallised from ethanol. Yield 1.96g (60%); m.p. 227° (d). (Found : C, 68.79; H, 6.75; S, 10.68%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{S}$: C, 68.69; H, 6.40; S, 10.77%). NMR(DMSO) : δ 1.28-1.41 [d, 6H; $>C(\text{CH}_3)_2$], δ 1.54 (s, 3H; $=\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$), δ 2.34-2.45 (d, 2H; $-\text{NH}_2$), δ 5.0 (s, 1H; $\text{C}=\text{CH}$), δ 6.95-8.40 (m, 6H; aromatic), δ 9.09-9.17 (d; 1H; $-\text{SH}$).

2, 2, 4-Trimethyl-2H, 12H-naphtho [1, 2-c] pyrimido 1, 2-e] 1, 2, 5 thiadiazine (V) :

To a stirred suspension of 1-(1'-amino-2'-naphthyl)-1, 4-dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-pyrimidine-2-thiol (1.80g; 0.006 mole) in dry carbon tetrachloride (50 ml), N-bromosuccinimide (1.18g; 0.0066 mole) was added over a period of 15 mins. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2 hrs. The brown solid began to float on the surface of the solvent. Solvent was removed under vacuum and the brown amorphous solid was treated with 5% sodium carbonate solution (50 ml) and washed with water (50 ml). Product obtained was purified by column chromatography (eluted with benzene-methanol mixture). Yield 0.62g. (35%); m.p. 260°(d). (Found : N, 14.35; S, 10.75%. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}$: N, 14.24; S, 10.85%).

2-Imino-3-(1'-nitro-2'-naphthyl)-4-phenyl- Δ 4-thiazoline hydrobromide (VI) :

1,4-Dihydro-4, 4, 6-trimethyl-1-(1'-nitro-2'-naphthyl)-pyrimidine-2-thiol (6.54g.; 0.02 mole) was added to a solution of phenacyl bromide (3.98g; 0.02 mole) in ethanol (50 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 36 hrs. The reddish solid thus recovered after the removal of the solvent, under vacuum, was washed with acetone (100 ml). Product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid. Yield 5.57g (65%); m.p. 312° (d). (Found : C, 52.99; H, 4.98; N, 10.11; Br, 18.46%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{SHBr}$: C, 53.27; H, 4.27; N, 9.81; Br, 18.69%). NMR(DMSO) : δ 7.25

(s, 6H; $\text{HC} = \text{C}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), δ 7.29 (s, 1HC=CH), δ 7.8-8.6 (m, 6H; aromatic), δ 10.0 (s, 2H; $>C = \overset{+}{\text{N}}\text{H}_2$).

3-(1'-Amino-2'-naphthyl)-2-imino-4-phenyl- Δ 4-thiazoline (VII) :

A stirred suspension of finely powdered stannous chloride (7.45g.; 0.033 mole) in hydrochloric acid (5 ml) was cooled to 5°, and 2-imino-3-(1'-nitro-2'-naphthyl)-4-phenyl- Δ 4-thiazoline hydrobromide (4.70g; 0.011 mole) was added at such a rate so that the temperature did not rise above 10°. After the complete addition the reaction mixture was refluxed for 24 hrs. White slurry thus obtained was poured on crushed ice and basified with 30% sodium hydroxide till precipitated stannous hydroxide redissolved.

Mixture was chilled for one hour and filtered. Product obtained was crystallised from aq. ethanol. Yield 2.1g. (60%); m.p. 120° (d). (Found: N, 12.97; S, 9.85%. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{15}N_3S$: N, 13.25; S, 10.10%).

3-Phenyl-11H-naphtho [2, 1-e] thiazolo [2, 3-c]-as-triazine (VIII);

Dry N-bromo-succinimide (1.18g.; 0.0066 mole) was slowly added to a stirred suspension of 3-(1'-amino-2'-naphthyl)-2-imino-4-phenyl- Δ^4 -thiazoline (1.90g.; 0.006 mole) in dry carbon tetrachloride (50ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed under dry conditions till the brown solid began to float on the surface of the solvent. The solvent was removed under vacuum and the solid thus obtained was treated with 5% sodium carbonate filtered and then washed with water. The product obtained was purified by column chromatography (eluted with benzene-methanol mixture). Yield 0.76g. (40%); m.p. 232° (d). (Found: C, 72.11;

H, 4.39%. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{13}N_3S$: C, 72.38; H, 4.13%).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.P.M.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the award of a research fellowship.

References

1. S. K. VASUDEVA, M. P. MAHAJAN, B. K. BANDHLISH and N. K. RALHAN, *Indian J. Chem.* 1973, **11**, 741.
2. S. K. VASUDEVA, M. P. MAHAJAN and N. K. RALHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 1204.
3. R. A. MATHES, F. D. STEWART and S. FRANK JR., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1452.
4. R. A. MATHES, F. D. STEWART and S. FRANK JR., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 1748.
5. L. HORNER and R. H. WINKEIMANN, *Angew. Chem.*, 1959, **71**, 349.
6. R. FILLER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1963, **63**, 21.
7. M. P. MAHAJAN, S. K. VASUDEVA and N. K. RALHAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 318.